

Ideal Gas Entropy as a Quasi-Deterministic Result of Removal of Time? Part 2

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Ideal gas entropy is often obtained through the a priori assumption that one must maximize \ln of the number of states possible when a total energy E is distributed among N particles, subject to the constraint that $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E$. This, in turn, is linked to the a priori assumption used in a microcanonical distribution that any energy distribution of E among N particles carries the same weight.

In Part 1, we tried to argue that these a priori statistical assumptions are really linked to the Newtonian mechanics of the problem. We focused on the removal of time measurements for a deterministic Newtonian particle with constant velocity in a container and argued that this removal of information is consistent with a volume of $2V$ having twice as much uncertainty as a volume of V . In other words, we were able to obtain this result without an a priori statistical argument that $2V$ has twice as many states as V .

Here, we try to argue that $p(e_i)$, where e_i is single particle energy, may be obtained without maximization of the number of states subject to an energy constraint in the following manner. One first assumes that a particle with energy e_i is also associated with many other properties as it comes in to collide with an e_j . For example, if one has a billiard ball, the point of contact and direction of the hit are important. If one has all of this information, we argue that the collision may be described in a deterministic manner. We next consider removing information to make the interaction problem simpler. In fact, only information about e_i is retained and it is assumed specifically for the collisions that all one needs to know is that energy is conserved. In other words, a statistical assumption is applied to the physical collisions with information removed and not to the number of states. If an average two-body collision is only dependent on $e_i + e_j$, then any $e_k + e_l = e_i + e_j$ is on the same footing as $e_i + e_j$. In other words, the average action of a collision potential with all information removed except conservation of energy dictates the type of probability distribution present, namely $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ which leads directly to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

Traditional View About the Number of States

Statistical mechanics is often presented in terms of a number of states view of a system. For example, in a microcanonical picture, one has an energy of E distributed over N particles and argues that any distribution carries the same probability weight. There is no focus on the dynamics and collisions and so this equal weight picture appears as an a priori assumption. In the canonical picture, one maximizes:

$$\ln(N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)!) \text{ subject to the constraint: } \sum_i e_i n(e_i)/N = E \quad ((1))$$

The volume probability is assumed to be a uniform $1/V$ ((2)). That is, the uniform distribution is associated with the maximum number of positions of a particle.

Removal Of Information for a Newtonian Description

In Part 1, we argued that for the uniform volume probability $1/V$, one does not need to consider the state view, i.e. break the volume into equal pieces and argue that one may be in one versus the other with equal probability.

Instead, we considered a Newtonian picture of two particles in 1-D boxes of sizes L and $2L$, starting at $x=0$, $t=0$ and moving with the same speed. We then argued that if one removes time from the Newtonian scenario, to simplify it by erasing information, then a given x point in L may map to various times. If one applies these times to the $2L$ box, one finds that they map to two distinct x points, for $3L$, three points etc. Thus, the idea of $p_1(V) = 1/V$ does not need to be obtained through the notion of states having equal weight, but can be found directly from removing information in a Newtonian scenario. Here we want to extend this idea to the energy part $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$.

Removal of Collision Information to Obtain $C \exp(-e_i/T)$

Newtonian mechanics is known for its deterministic description of interactions with a potential $V(x)$. Even in the case of billiards, strikes to different parts of the ball, together with rolling conditions lead to detailed results. These detailed descriptions, however, require carrying more information than simply e_i of the particle. One may ask: What happens if I try to remove all information about a collision except e_i values? For a two body collision of e_i with e_j , one may argue that the minimal information required is e_i with the constraint conservation of energy, $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$. Thus, this is a description based on removing all details except one about the two body collision. This leads to a loss of determinism. Since only e_i is kept as information, one expects a $p(e_i)$ to exist, but it is the property of the potential in conserving energy that leads to the result:

$$p(e_i) p(e_j) = p(e_i + e_j) \text{ unnormalized } ((3))$$

From ((3)), one has: $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ by comparing it with $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$, i.e. the energy conservation condition which is the only information regarding the collision that one retains.

We argue that ideal gas statistical mechanics seems to follow directly from removing specific information from a Newtonian deterministic description and then asking: What specific consequences does this have on probabilities of the remaining information? In the case of volume one has $p_1(V) = 1/V$ and in the case of $p(e_i)$, $C \exp(-e_i/T)$. In other words, it seems that ideal gas law statistical mechanics does not need to be thought of in terms of states together with a priori statistical assumptions.

The state picture seems to be a mapping of this result, but uses a priori statistical assumptions (equal weights etc), that must be compatible with the Newtonian interactions with information removed. In other words, these are not really a priori statistical assumptions which seem reasonable, but really assumptions which follow from the average behaviour of interaction potentials which arise when some details of the collision are removed. We argue that this is why one has some derivations which use maximization of \ln of the number of states and others

which use reaction balance. We suggest that it is really a removal of information in collisions, followed by constraints associated with the remaining information which lead to a statistical view. In other words, e_i, e_j is the remaining information left for a two-body collision and its conservation (of $e_i + e_j$) is the constraint. In such a view, it is not the case of reaction balance versus maximization of states subject to a constraint.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to investigate how statistical mechanics arises from Newtonian mechanics in an ideal gas case. We note that traditionally the idea of maximization of the \ln of the number of states: $\ln(N! / \prod_i n_i!)$ subject to $\sum_i n_i p_i = E$ or reaction balance is used. We argue that neither of these approaches is directly linked to a deterministic Newtonian description of the problem. For example, even if one uses reaction balance which at least considers two-body scattering, one still has the problem of finding $p_1(V) = 1/V$. This suggests that there should be a systematic way to obtain statistical mechanics for an ideal gas from deterministic Newtonian mechanics.

In Part 1, we argued that one does not need to break a volume into cells and argue that $2V$ has twice as many cells as V in order to find $p_1(V) = 1/V$. We noted that one may remove time measurements for a particle in Newtonian mechanics to find that in V (or L) an x point corresponds to various possible times such that these correspond to two distinct x points in $2L$ etc.

Here, we argue that retaining many parameters for a particle allows one to determine a two-body collision deterministically, i.e. without any probability. We then ask: What is the minimal information one needs to keep for such a collision? Removing other information leads to a statistical picture with probabilities controlled by a constraint associated with the minimal information retained. We argue that the minimal information is e_i , and that the constraint is that $e_i + e_j$ is conserved. This leads to $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ if $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$. From this follows the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. Thus, statistical mechanics seems to follow from removal of information from deterministic Newtonian mechanics leading to a probability which is constrained by the effects of the removal of specific information from the Newtonian picture rather than from a priori assumptions about states. The view of the states seems to be a mapping from the information-removed Newtonian picture.